

A Study of Entrepreneurial Intentions among Tourism Students

1) Verda Khan

Research Scholar, Department of Commerce, Aligarh Muslim University, Aligarh, India

2) Shahzar Ali Khan

Research Scholar, Department of Commerce, Aligarh Muslim University, Aligarh, India

3) S.M Imamul Haque

Professor, Department of Commerce, Aligarh Muslim University, Aligarh, India

Corresponding Author: Shahzar Ali Khan

khanshahzar54@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

The purpose of the current study is to conceptually highlight the factors that influence the entrepreneurial intention of tourism students. Additionally, this study identified the main theories that are typically applied to forecast the entrepreneurial intentions of these students. This paper is entirely based on a review of available literature related to the entrepreneurial intention of tourism students. Shapero & Sokol's Entrepreneurial Event Model and Ajzen's Theory of Planned Behaviour are found to be the most frequently used theories in these studies to predict tourism students' entrepreneurial intentions. Entrepreneurship education is found to be one of the most crucial elements in assisting students to understand entrepreneurship and influencing their desire to launch their own enterprises. The entrepreneurial intent of tourism students is also found to be influenced by personality traits (leadership, risk-taking propensity, locus of control, tolerance of ambiguity, need for achievement, innovativeness, and self-efficacy), demographic characteristics (gender, family background), and motivating factors such as professional autonomy, fulfilment of personal visions, achieving personal assets, searching for new challenges, role models, social capital among others. The current study adds to the existing body of knowledge and offers insight into the various factors influencing the entrepreneurial intent of tourism students so that actions could be taken appropriately to translate this intention into behaviour, which in turn would create more job opportunities and produce a positive economic outcome.

Received: 2 July 2023

Revised: 18 July 2023

Final Accepted 26 July 2023

Copyright © authors 2023

357

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8191341>

INTRODUCTION

In the past twenty years, there has been a notable increase in scholarly investigations pertaining to entrepreneurship and entrepreneurial intentions. This surge in academic research can be attributed to the rise of diverse initiatives and policies aimed at fostering and bolstering entrepreneurial endeavours, the advancements in science and technology (Khan et al., 2023b), and the provision of financial incentives. The concept of entrepreneurship encompasses the process of recognizing and harnessing potential opportunities that ultimately culminate in the creation and development of novel business enterprises (Ahmad et al., 2019). The significance of entrepreneurship in the context of economic development cannot be overstated. This dynamic process plays a pivotal role in stimulating innovation, propelling technological advancements, generating employment opportunities, and fortifying the foundations of economic structures (Soliman, 2011). Policymakers across various nations, encompassing both affluent and developing economies, have dedicated substantial efforts and resources towards fostering entrepreneurial endeavours. This strategic focus stems from the multitude of favourable consequences associated with entrepreneurial activity, particularly its potential to generate employment opportunities and alleviate poverty (Kibuka, 2011).

Tourism is a widely recognized economic activity that holds immense global significance. There are few domains that can boast such widespread engagement, both directly and indirectly, as the one under consideration. The tourism industry plays a pivotal role in stimulating economic growth by facilitating the establishment of new enterprises and supporting the growth of pre-existing ones. Additionally, it serves as a catalyst for infrastructure development and presents numerous avenues for local communities to engage in micro and small-scale entrepreneurial activities. The tourism industry provides entrepreneurs with a conducive and attractive environment for business endeavours (Getz and Petersen, 2005). The tourism industry plays a significant role in fostering regional economic growth. By actively supporting and motivating students pursuing studies in tourism, we can facilitate the transformation of their entrepreneurial aspirations into concrete entrepreneurial actions. This, in turn, can lead to the creation of additional employment opportunities and generate a favourable economic outcome (Zhang et al., 2020). Despite the fact that the covid-19 pandemic had an impact on every part of the tourism and hospitality sector (Khan et al.,

2022), including the development of entrepreneurship, it also offered new business opportunities, enabling entrepreneurs to compete in a highly competitive market.

From a psychological standpoint, the level of an individual's engagement in entrepreneurial endeavours can be most accurately anticipated by their intention, which serves as the primary motivator for establishing a novel business venture. The possession of entrepreneurial intention is a crucial characteristic that individuals must have in order to initiate establishing a new enterprise. The emergence of entrepreneurial intention stems from an individual's intrinsic inclination to pursue entrepreneurship as a profession. University students are commonly perceived as individuals with the potential to become entrepreneurs (Hou et al., 2019), thus prompting numerous studies exploring their intentions towards entrepreneurship in the academic literature. However, it is worth noting that studies on entrepreneurial intention among students enrolled in tourism courses are few.

This article presents a comprehensive analysis and evaluation of the current body of literature related to the entrepreneurial intentions of tourism students. The key objectives of this research paper are twofold; firstly, it sheds light on the predominant theories that are commonly employed to forecast the entrepreneurial intentions of students pursuing studies in tourism. Secondly, it seeks to offer a comprehensive understanding of the various factors that affects the entrepreneurial intentions of students studying in the field of tourism.

THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

The phenomenon of entrepreneurship is widely regarded as a manifestation of deliberate intention and strategic behaviour. Consequently, the significance of theories and models that forecast and elucidate individuals' inclination towards engaging in entrepreneurial activities has witnessed a notable surge. The theories most commonly employed in the prediction of entrepreneurial intention among students in the tourism field are the Entrepreneurial Event Model (EEM) by Shapero & Sokol (1982) and the Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB) by Ajzen (1991).

Entrepreneurial Event Model

The Entrepreneurial Event Model proposed by Shapero and Sokol in 1982 is widely recognized as one of the earliest intention models focusing on entrepreneurship. The

underlying principle of this theoretical framework posits that a nascent enterprise can be comprehensively elucidated by examining the intricate interplay of various factors that exert influence on an individual's behaviour. According to this model, the determination of an individual to initiate a new business venture is influenced by three distinct factors, namely perceived desirability, perceived feasibility, and propensity to act. The concept of perceived desirability pertains to the level of appeal that an individual associates with engaging in a particular behaviour (Ahmad et al., 2019). On the other hand, perceived feasibility encompasses an individual's perceptions regarding their own ability to successfully carry out a specific behaviour (Ahmad et al., 2019). According to Shapero and Sokol (1982), it has been observed that individuals' perception of alternative options is significantly influenced by their underlying value system. This value system, in turn, is predominantly shaped by various social as well as cultural variables.

In a study conducted by Ahmad et al. (2019), it was discovered that there exists a positive correlation between the perceived desirability and perceived feasibility factors and the entrepreneurial intentions of students specializing in the field of tourism. The findings of Esfandiar et al. (2019) further corroborated the presence of a positive relationship between perceived desirability and perceived feasibility and the subsequent impact on the entrepreneurial intentions of students pursuing a career in the tourism industry. This study's findings also indicated a positive relationship between perceived opportunity and entrepreneurial intentions, which becomes more pronounced when an individual has a strong propensity to act.

Theory of Planned Behaviour

The Theory of Planned Behaviour (Ajzen, 1991) is a well-established psychological framework frequently employed to elucidate and predict human behaviour. This theory offers valuable insights into the factors that influence an individual's actions and provides a robust framework for understanding and forecasting their behavioural patterns (Khan et al., 2023a). According to the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB), the individual's intention to engage in a particular behaviour is a significant predictor of their subsequent action. This intention is influenced by several factors, including their attitude towards the behaviour, subjective norms, and perceived behavioural control (Ajzen, 1991).

According to Ajzen (1991), attitude refers to an individual's inclination to react either positively or negatively towards a specific object or concept. According to Ajzen (1991), a subjective norm is a construct which is influenced by the opinions of important others, including family and friends. Perceived behavioural control refers to the extent to which an individual contemplates their ability to execute or abstain from a particular behaviour while also perceiving a sense of control over it (Khan et al., 2023a). Based on empirical evidence, it can be posited that an individual's level of perceived behavioural control is directly proportional to the likelihood of engaging in a particular behaviour. In other words, the stronger one's belief in their ability to successfully execute a specific behaviour, the greater the probability of them actually demonstrating that behaviour (Engle et al., 2010).

The empirical findings of Phuc et al. (2020) indicated that subjective norms, attitude toward entrepreneurship, and perceived behavioural control exert significant direct effects on the entrepreneurial intention of students specializing in the field of tourism. However, Mei et al. (2016) indicated that variations exist in personal attitude, subjective norms, and perceived behavioural control based on distinct personal variables.

FACTORS AFFECTING ENTREPRENEURIAL INTENTIONS OF TOURISM STUDENTS

Studies have been conducted in different countries to investigate the entrepreneurial intention among students pursuing studies in the field of tourism. These studies have identified several factors that exert an influence on the entrepreneurial intention exhibited by students.

Entrepreneurship Education

The importance of entrepreneurship education has been acknowledged as one of the key elements that aid students in properly comprehending what entrepreneurship is (Phuc et al., 2020). Entrepreneurship programmes have been observed to significantly impact students' self-perception of their capacity to engage in entrepreneurial endeavours and their recognition of areas in which their managerial skills may require enhancement (Ahmed & Kayat, 2019; Bagheri & Pihie, 2011; Zovko et al., 2020). Universities and faculties have been actively adapting to the ever-changing landscape by developing and offering entrepreneurial courses (Zovko et al., 2020). Additionally, they have established entrepreneurial incubators to support

and guide aspiring entrepreneurs, and funding associations have also emerged to promote entrepreneurship through various programs and initiatives (Zovko et al., 2020). These concerted efforts aim to foster an environment conducive to entrepreneurial endeavours and ultimately contribute to the overall prosperity of society. The disposition and level of understanding regarding entrepreneurship are anticipated to influence individuals' propensity to initiate their own business endeavours in the foreseeable future (Wang & Wong, 2004).

Personality Traits

Previous studies have established a positive correlation between personality traits and entrepreneurial intention, suggesting that specific personality traits play a significant role in determining one's inclination towards entrepreneurship (Koh, 1996). These studies involved the utilization of distinct personality traits among students to evaluate and determine the levels of entrepreneurial characteristics exhibited by the participants. These attributes include leadership, risk-taking propensity, locus of control, tolerance of ambiguity, need for achievement, innovativeness, and self-efficacy. Gurel et al. (2010) also found that there exists a statistically significant correlation between innovation, propensity to take risks, and entrepreneurial intention of tourism students. In their study, Borges et al. (2021) indicated that students who possess strong leadership qualities, demonstrate creativity, and have a strong desire for achievement are more likely to prioritize entrepreneurship as their initial choice when entering the job market. Altinay et al. (2012) found that the innovativeness and entrepreneurial intentions of hospitality students are positively related; however, no association of tolerance of ambiguity, locus of control, need for achievement, and risk-taking propensity was found with entrepreneurial intention.

Demographic factors

Numerous studies have emphasized the importance of demographic factors in affecting students' intentions to become entrepreneurs (Butkouskaya et al., 2020; Çelik et al., 2021; Dao et al., 2021; de la Cruz del Río-Rama et al., 2017; Jovicic-Vukovic et al., 2020; Mei et al., 2016; Moreno-Gómez et al., 2022; Muñoz-Fernández et al., 2017). The likelihood of starting a business is influenced by one's gender. Studies have found that male students are likelier to start their own businesses than female students (Butkouskaya et al., 2020; Muñoz-Fernández et al., 2017). Family background also influences the entrepreneurial intention of

students. Working in a family business gives people the knowledge and experience they need to launch their own company or grow it together with their families, particularly in the tourism sector, where family enterprises have always played a significant role (Getz & Carlsen, 2005). Individuals who grow up in an entrepreneurial atmosphere are more inclined to favour entrepreneurship than others (Carr & Sequeira, 2007). Similarly, education level, age, and place of residence are among the demographic factors that also predict tourism students' entrepreneurial intent.

Motivational Factors

Several additional factors may serve as motivators for students to choose entrepreneurship as their preferred career path. A study conducted by Atef & Al-Balushi (2015) revealed several pull and push factors that affect the entrepreneurial intention of tourism students. The three primary pull factors that have been identified in this study are income, education, and a stable job. Sidorkiewicz (2021), in their study, indicated that the respondents identified several key factors that served as strong motivators for embarking on entrepreneurial endeavours. These factors include professional autonomy, the potential for greater financial gains compared to traditional employment arrangements, and the fulfilment of personal aspirations. Another study by de la Cruz del Río-Rama et al. (2017) revealed that the primary drivers that motivate students pursuing a degree in tourism to establish their own businesses have been identified as follows: the opportunity to cultivate and implement their own innovative concepts, the pursuit of novel and stimulating endeavours, and the desire to establish a venture that is personally fulfilling and financially rewarding. In addition to the factors mentioned above, there are other factors that have an impact on the entrepreneurial intention of tourism students. These factors include role models (Ân, 2019), parents' attitudes (Liu & Zhao, 2021), and social capital (Chia & Liang, 2016).

CONCLUSION

Entrepreneurial activities and innovative changes are the solutions for solving the challenges of the 21st century by providing sustainable development, generating jobs, increasing employment opportunities and economic development. Several institutions and policy-making bodies are working hard to cultivate entrepreneurship spirit among the students. Still,

the percentage of students opting for entrepreneurship as a career is found to be less than the expected level.

The tourism industry contributes to the country's economic development and regional economic development, as the industry includes transportation, catering, shopping, and many others (Hoi et al., 2018). Stimulating the entrepreneurial intention of tourism students can help convert this intention into entrepreneurial behaviour and consequently lead to more job opportunities and the development of the whole economy (Altinay et al., 2012). Therefore, exploring the factors impacting tourism students' entrepreneurial intention is essential. After thoroughly reviewing the available literature, the researchers found several factors that influence the entrepreneurial intention of tourism students. One of the most important factors that help students understand what entrepreneurship is and influences students' inclination to start their own businesses is entrepreneurship education. Additionally, personality traits (leadership, risk-taking propensity, locus of control, tolerance of ambiguity, need for achievement, innovativeness, and self-efficacy) are also important in predicting one's propensity for entrepreneurship. Demographic characteristics (gender, family background etc.) are also found to have an impact on the entrepreneurial intent of tourism students. It was also found that several factors may motivate students to pursue entrepreneurship as a career, such as professional autonomy, fulfilment of personal visions, achieving personal assets, searching for new challenges, role models, social capital etc.

This study additionally identified the primary theories that are frequently used to predict the entrepreneurial intentions of students studying tourism degrees. The Entrepreneurial Event Model (EEM) by Shapero & Sokol (1982) and the Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB) by Ajzen (1991) are the two theories that are most frequently used to predict the entrepreneurial intention of tourism students.

This paper provides an overview of the factors that influence the entrepreneurial intention of tourism students and the theories used in these studies. As this paper is entirely based on a review of the allied literature, future research may conduct a bibliometric analysis or systematic analysis to provide a more comprehensive overview.

References

Received: 2 July 2023

Revised: 18 July 2023

Final Accepted 26 July 2023

Copyright © authors 2023

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8191341>

- Ahmad, N. H., Ramayah, T., Mahmud, I., Musa, M., & Anika, J. J. (2019). Entrepreneurship as a preferred career option: Modelling tourism students' entrepreneurial intention. *Education + Training*, 61(9), 1151–1169. <https://doi.org/10.1108/ET-12-2018-0269>
- Ahmed, M. R. M., & Kayat, K. (2019). Boosting Entrepreneurial Intentions Among Female Tourism Students Through Social Support and Entrepreneurial Self-Efficacy in Egypt: Can Entrepreneurship Education Moderate? *Journal of Basic and Applied Research International*, 25(6), 376–385.
- Ajzen, I. (1991). The theory of planned behavior. *Organizational Behavior and Human Decision Processes*, 50(2), 179–211. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0749-5978\(91\)90020-T](https://doi.org/10.1016/0749-5978(91)90020-T)
- Altinay, L., Madanoglu, M., Daniele, R., & Lashley, C. (2012). The influence of family tradition and psychological traits on entrepreneurial intention. *International Journal of Hospitality Management*, 31(2), 489–499. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhm.2011.07.007>
- Ân, L. T. N. (2019). *The influence of entrepreneurial desire and self-efficacy on entrepreneurial intention: A study in the context of tourism and hospitality students*. University of Otago.
- Atef, T. M., & Al-Balushi, M. (2015). Entrepreneurship as a means for restructuring employment patterns. *Tourism and Hospitality Research*, 15(2), 73–90. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1467358414558082>
- Bagheri, A., & Pihie, Z. A. L. (2011). On Becoming an Entrepreneurial Leader: A Focus on the Impacts of University Entrepreneurship Programs. *American Journal of Applied Sciences*, 8(9), 884–892. <https://doi.org/10.3844/ajassp.2011.884.892>
- Butkouskaya, V., Romagosa, F., & Noguera, M. (2020). Obstacles to Sustainable Entrepreneurship amongst Tourism Students: A Gender Comparison. *Sustainability*, 12(5), 1812. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su12051812>
- Carr, J. C., & Sequeira, J. M. (2007). Prior family business exposure as intergenerational influence and entrepreneurial intent: A Theory of Planned Behavior approach. *Journal of Business Research*, 60(10), 1090–1098. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2006.12.016>

- Çelik, A. K., Yıldız, T., Aykanat, Z., & Kazemzadeh, S. (2021). The impact of narrow personality traits on entrepreneurial intention in developing countries: A comparison of Turkish and Iranian undergraduate students using ordered discrete choice models. *European Research on Management and Business Economics*, 27(1), 100138. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.iedeen.2020.100138>
- Chia, C.-C., & Liang, C. (2016). Influence of Creativity and Social Capital on the Entrepreneurial Intention of Tourism Students. *Journal of Entrepreneurship, Management and Innovation*, 12(2), 151–168.
- Chye Koh, H. (1996). Testing hypotheses of entrepreneurial characteristics: A study of Hong Kong MBA students. *Journal of Managerial Psychology*, 11(3), 12–25. <https://doi.org/10.1108/02683949610113566>
- Dao, T. K., Bui, A. T., Doan, T. T. T., Dao, N. T., Le, H. H., & Le, T. T. H. (2021). Impact of academic majors on entrepreneurial intentions of Vietnamese students: An extension of the theory of planned behavior. *Heliyon*, 7(3), E06381. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2021.e06381>
- de la Cruz del Río-Rama, M., Álvarez-García, J., Rueda-Armengot, C., & Peris-Ortiz, M. (2017). Entrepreneurship by Students in Tourism Degree Program. A Cross-Cultural Analysis. In *Entrepreneurial Universities* (pp. 267–286). Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-47949-1_19
- Engle, R. L., Dimitriadi, N., Gavidia, J. V., Schlaegel, C., Delanoe, S., Alvarado, I., He, X., Buame, S., & Wolff, B. (2010). Entrepreneurial intent : A twelve country evaluation of Ajzen' s model on planned behavior. *International Journal of Entrepreneurial Behavior & Research*, 16(1), 35–57. <https://doi.org/10.1108/13552551011020063>
- Esfandiar, K., Sharifi-Tehrani, M., Pratt, S., & Altinay, L. (2019). Understanding entrepreneurial intentions: A developed integrated structural model approach. *Journal of Business Research*, 94, 172–182. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2017.10.045>
- Getz, D., & Carlsen, J. (2005). Family business in tourism: State of the Art. *Annals of Tourism Research*, 32(1), 237–258. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.annals.2004.07.006>

- Getz, D., & Petersen, T. (2005). Growth and profit-oriented entrepreneurship among family business owners in the tourism and hospitality industry. *International Journal of Hospitality Management*, 24(2), 219–242. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhm.2004.06.007>
- Gurel, E., Altinay, L., & Daniele, R. (2010). Tourism students' entrepreneurial intentions. *Annals of Tourism Research*, 37(3), 646–669. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.annals.2009.12.003>
- Hoi, V., Fong, I., Anthony, I., Fok, J., & Hong, L. (2018). Developing institutional logics in the tourism industry through coopetition. *Tourism Management*, 66, 244–262. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tourman.2017.12.005>
- Hou, F., Su, Y., Lu, M., & Qi, M. (2019). Model of the Entrepreneurial Intention of University Students in the Pearl River Delta of China. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 10. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2019.00916>
- Jovicic-Vukovic, A., Josanov-Vrgovic, I., Jovin, S., & Papic-Blagojevic, N. (2020). Socio-demographic characteristics and students' entrepreneurial intentions. *Stanovnistvo*, 58(2), 57–75. <https://doi.org/10.2298/STNV200423007J>
- Khan, M. A., Khan, S. A., & Khan, V. (2022). Impact of Covid-19 Pandemic on Tourists' Behavior and Preferences: A Critical Insight. *South Asian Journal of Social Science and Humanities*, 3(4), 123–137. <https://doi.org/10.48165/sajssh.2022.3410>
- Khan, S. A., Khan, V., & Khan, M. A. (2023a). Behavioural intention of tourists towards volunteer tourism: A developing country perspective. *Journal of Tourism, Heritage & Services Marketing*, 9(1), 37–47.
- Khan, S. A., Khan, V., & Khan, M. A. (2023b). Technology as a Catalyst for Tourism Entrepreneurship: A Critical Insight. *International Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities Invention*, 10(04), 7832–7838. <https://doi.org/10.18535/ijsshi/v10i04.01>
- Kibuka, G. (2011). *An examination of factors that influence entrepreneurial intention of high school students in Kenya*. University of Illinois.
- Liu, X., & Zhao, W. G. W. (2021). Family education? Unpacking parental factors for tourism

- and hospitality students' entrepreneurial intention. *Journal of Hospitality, Leisure, Sport & Tourism Education*, 29, 100284. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhlste.2020.100284>
- Mei, H., Zhan, Z., Fong, P. S. W., Liang, T., & Ma, Z. (2016). Planned behaviour of tourism students' entrepreneurial intentions in China. *Applied Economics*, 48(13), 1240–1254. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00036846.2015.1096006>
- Moreno-Gómez, J., Gómez-Araujo, E., Ferrer-Ortíz, D., & Peña-Ruiz, R. (2022). Gender perspective of parental role model influence on nascent entrepreneurs: Evidence from Colombia. *European Research on Management and Business Economics*, 28(1), 100156. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.iedeen.2021.100156>
- Muñoz-Fernández, G. A., Rodríguez-Gutiérrez, P., & Santos-Roldán, L. (2017). Entrepreneurship in Higher Education in Tourism, gender issue? *Electronic Journal of Research in Education Psychology*, 14(38), 45–66. <https://doi.org/10.14204/ejrep.38.15040>
- Phuc, P. T., Vinh, N. Q., & Do, Q. H. (2020). Factors affecting entrepreneurial intention among tourism undergraduate students in Vietnam. *Management Science Letters*, 10(15), 3675–3682. <https://doi.org/10.5267/j.msl.2020.6.026>
- Shapero, A., & Sokol, L. (1982). The Social Dimensions of Entrepreneurship. *University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign's Academy for Entrepreneurial Leadership Historical Research Reference in Entrepreneurship*.
- Sidorkiewicz, M. (2021). Factors stimulating and destimulating the level of tourism and recreational entrepreneurship among students. *Procedia Computer Science*, 192, 1422–1430. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procs.2021.08.145>
- Soliman, D. M. (2011). Entrepreneurial Intention Among Tourism Undergraduate Students in Egypt. *Tourism Analysis*, 16(4), 471–481. <https://doi.org/10.3727/108354211X13149079789052>
- Wang, C. K., & Wong, P.-K. (2004). Entrepreneurial interest of university students in Singapore. *Technovation*, 24(2), 163–172. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0166-4972\(02\)00016-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0166-4972(02)00016-0)

Zhang, S.-N., Li, Y.-Q., Liu, C.-H., & Ruan, W.-Q. (2020). Critical factors identification and prediction of tourism and hospitality students' entrepreneurial intention. *Journal of Hospitality, Leisure, Sport & Tourism Education*, 26, 100234.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhlste.2019.100234>

Zovko, L., Bilić, I., & Dulčić, Ž. (2020). Determinants of students' entrepreneurial intention: an empirical research. *Management*, 25(1), 25–44.

<https://doi.org/10.30924/mjcmi.25.1.2>